

A Study to Evaluate the Effectiveness of Hot Water Application with Epsom Salt among Old Age with Joint Pain at Selected Areas at Kondapur, Sangareddy Dist. TS

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom salt among old age with joint pain.

Objectives

1. To assess the level of pain in both Experimental and Control group by pretest.
2. To administer hot water application with Epsom Salt in Experimental group
3. To evaluate the effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom salt in Experimental group.
4. Find out association between pretest , posttest level of pain with selected socio demographic variables in experimental and control group.

Results

The mean pretest pain score M (9.30+/-SD 0.702+/-) was less than the posttest pain score M(3.10+/- SD 1.539+/-) paired t value 19.191, table 2.045 computed between the pretest and posttest level of knowledge core which was significantly at 0.000 level. So that calculated t value Is greater than table t value. The research Hypothesis (H) indicates that hot water application with Epsom Salt among old age with joint pain was effective.

Interpretation and conclusion

The study was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom salt among old age with joint pain at selected areas overall old age with joint pain has affected in decrease the level of joint pain.

INTRODUCTION

Most of the adult health problems manifested through pain. The article reported especially the pain is the major symptom of most musculoskeletal disorders. The pain may be mild or severe, local, or diffuse, depending on where the injury occurred. Although pain may be acute and short-lived, as is the case with most injuries, pain may be ongoing with chronic illnesses, such as joint pain.^[1] Pain is defined as an unpleasant sensation occurring in varying degrees of severity because of injury, disease, or emotional disorder. But the pain is more than unpleasant sensations. Pain is a major component part of your nervous system. Pain is a perception, and a bodily state. Despite its unpleasantness, pain is a critical component of the body's defense system. It is part of a rapid warning and defense relay instructing the motor neurons of the central nervous system to minimize detected physical harm.

Joint pain is a chronic, systemic inflammatory disorder that may affect many tissues & organs but principally attacks the joints produce an inflammatory synovitis that often progresses to destruction of articular cartilage and ankylosis of the joints. It also produces diffuse inflammation in lungs, pericardium, pleura & sclera. Onset is more frequent between the ages of 40 and 50. It can be disabling and painful, which can lead to substantial loss of functioning and mobility.^[2]

In most cases arthritis pain and inflammation cannot be avoided as the body ages. In fact, most people over the age of 50 show some signs of arthritis. Joints naturally degenerate over time. Fortunately, arthritis can be managed through a combination of medication, exercise, rest, weight-management, nutrition, and, in some cases, surgery etc. Arthritis is a chronic disease that will remain for a long time and for the rest of life. The treatments will change over time and medication may be adjusted. Having a positive mental outlook and the support of family and friends will help to live with arthritis and be able to continue to perform daily activities. Arthritis is not just disease; it is a complex disorder that comprises more than 100 distinct conditions and can affect people at any stage of life. Two of the most common forms are osteoarthritis and joint pain.

Some complications of arthritis include joint stiffness, social complications, reduced physical activity, reduced leisure activity etc. Joint pain due to arthritis can limit sexual activity. Joint pain affects the quality of life. The complications of Joint pain include joint distraction, heart failure, lung disease, low or high platelets, spine instability etc. Affected joints may worsen the ordinary tasks of day-to-day life. Joint pain complications of this disease may shorten survival in some individuals.

Pain too is part of the body's defense system; it triggers mental problem-solving strategies that seek to end the painful experience. Pain intensity may range from slight through severe to agonizing; it is experienced as having qualities such as sharp, throbbing, dull, nauseating, burning, and shooting. It often has both an emotional quality and a sensed bodily location.

Pain can be classified as acute or chronic. The distinction between acute and chronic is not based on the duration of the sensation, but rather on the pain itself. The primary distinction is that an acute pain serves to protect one, e.g., after an injury. Whereas chronic pain does not serve this or any other purpose and is the disease of pain.

Joint pain is a common musculoskeletal disorder affecting 80% of people at some point in their lives. In India it is the most common cause of job-related disability and the second most common neurological ailment- only headache is more common. It can be acute, sub-acute (or) chronic in duration. With conservative measures, the symptoms of joint pain typically show significant improvement within a few weeks of onset. ^[3]

Pain in the joint is a common concern, affecting up to 90% of Americans at some point in their lifetime. Up to 50% will have more than one episode. Joint pain is not a specific disease, rather it is a symptom that may occur from a variety of different processes. In up to 85% of people with joint pain, despite a thorough medical examination, no specific cause of the pain can be identified.

what differs from normal aging changes. It usually presents joint pain with structural changes, crepitus, bony enlargements, deformity, instability, and restriction of movements may occur. Associated muscular weakness and wasting may also occur. Morning stiffness is a common complaint but usually brief 5-15 minutes but not exceeding 30 minutes. It is seen most in clinical practice usually one of the compartments of knee joint bears the brunt's of attack of the disease, obesity and female sex are common risk factors. Although there is no known cure for most forms of arthritis, treatment designed for individual patients can reduce/eliminate symptoms and limit functional impairment. The goals of contemporary management of arthritis extend beyond pain control to the enhancement of clients' functional status and health-related quality of life. ^[4]

The article from the home remedies for arthritis reported that. *Boswellia serrata* also known as shallaki improves blood circulation and relieves joint pain and swelling, take 5 grams of *Ashwagandha* powder twice a day with lukewarm water, *guduchi* juice is also beneficial in relieving joint pain,

take bath with Epsom salt warm water. it will relieve joint pains, strengthen bones, and improves blood circulations, some common herbs used in joint pain are *Saunth* (dried ginger), *guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia*), *rasna*, *errand* (*ricinus communis*), *shallaki* (*Boswellia serrata*) and *guggulu* (*commiphora mukul*). ^[5]

Non-pharmacological treatment includes the patient education regarding joint protection and avoidance of excessive joint loading which is important for these clients. Physical measures like hot pack, paraffin bath, clove oil massage, topical application of *goggalu*. loading is important for this patient. Physical measures like hot pack, paraffin bath or occupational therapies may be helpful.

The National Centre of complementary and alternative medicine have defined complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) as "a group of diverse medical and healthcare systems, practices, and products that are not presently considered to be part of conventional medicine. For some CAM practices, there is scientific evidence that a treatment is both beneficial and safe. Most clients who use complementary and alternative medicine treatments were not dissatisfied with conventional or established medical treatments but find that complementary medicine appeals to their values and beliefs about health.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

The epidemiological data on health problems in elderly reported as follows: Poor Vision (45.4%), Hypertension (38.2%), joint pains (36.1%), Bowel complaints (31.6%), Depression (23.6%), Difficulty in Hearing (20.5%), Weight Loss (19.6%), Anemia (16.8%), Urinary complaints (13.4%), Diabetes (13.3%), Fall (8.7%), II-ID (7.7%), Asthma (6.6%), COPD (4.8%), and Tuberculosis (3.1%) were the common health problems highlighted by the study. [7]. Since old age clients are more prone to develop complications of non-steroidal anti-Inflammatory drugs, physicians should be careful in selecting proper drugs on individual basis looking into the cost, efficacy, and toxic profile. However, paracetamol may be tried initially as an analgesic in osteoarthritis. Other NSAIDs can be used especially newer selective cyclooxygenase II (Cox-II) inhibitors. Locally applied NSAIDs are also useful but the drugs have severe side effects. Instead of using their drugs home remedies can be practice which is effective and safe.

Most people do not get enough magnesium, which can affect their nerve, muscle and enzyme function, contributing to pain and inflammation that can affect your back, and according to the Epsom Salt Council. Soaking in Epsom salt is one of the best ways to get its benefits, since your body doesn't process ingested magnesium as efficiently as it does absorb magnesium.

On the physical side, Epsom salt, which is the mineral magnesium sulfate, has been found to help alleviate pain. Additionally, soaking in Epsom Salt and Epsom salt compress helps to pull toxins from the body, which speeds the healing process. When a cold or the flu is coming on, adding Epsom Salt to a before-bed bath can often stop the virus in its track. Doctors usually refer to joint pain as acute if it has been presence for less than a month and chronic if it lasts for a longer period. Joint pain is one of the most common medical problems affecting 8 out of 10 people at some point during their lives. Joint pain can range from a dull, constant ache to a sudden, sharp pain.

From the above review and from the researcher's own observation, the researcher found that the hot water application is highly effective in relieving pain in the joints. Few studies support the benefit of Epsom salt hot water application. In this study the investigator planned to conduct the study to evaluate the effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom salt for reducing joint pain in old age clients.

From the above review and from the researcher's own observation, the researcher found that the hot water application is highly effective in relieving pain in the joints. In this study the investigator plans to conduct the study to evaluate the effectiveness of Epsom salt hot water application and plain hot water application for joint pain.

Statement of the Problem

A study to evaluate the effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom salt among old age with joint pain at selected areas at Kondapur, Sangareddy Dist. Ts.

OBJECTIVES

1. To assess the level of pain in both experimental and control group by pretest
2. To administer hot water application with Epsom salt in experimental group.
3. To evaluate the effectiveness of Hot water application with Epsom salt in experimental group.
4. Find out association between pretest and posttest level of pain with selected socio demographic variables in experimental and control group.

HYPOTHESES

1. H1 there will be a significant mean difference in the pretest pain score and posttest among experimental group.
2. H2 There will be a significant mean difference in the pretest pain score and posttest among control group.
3. H3 There will be a significant mean difference in the post test pain score between experimental group and control group.
4. There will a significant association between experimental group and control group with their demographic variables such as age, sex, occupation, duration of illness, using other home remedies.

Operational Definitions

1. Evaluate: Assess the level of joint pain after the hot applications with Epsom salt.
2. Effectiveness: It is the desired results produced by an action; effectiveness refers to extent to which hot water application has achieved desired effect in relieving of pain among old age which is measured standardized tool by investigator.
3. Hot Water Application with Epsom salt: Epsom salt is one of the home remedies which is rich in magnesium. Epsom salt compress was prepared by adding 30gms of Epsom salt to one liter of boiling water. This compress is applied to the joints with a cloth.
4. Joint Pain: In this study pain for the joints due to stiffness of the joint tenders, ligaments and muscles, it may be due to the degenerative disease of the joint.
5. Old age: Those who fall in the age group of 60 years and above both male and female having joint pain.

Assumption

1. Hot applications relieve pain, inflammation, and congestion.
2. Epsom salt has analgesic properties.
3. Epsom salt is easy to available in low cost.
4. Reducing the pain and meeting the comfort needs of old age.

Delimitation

1. The study was delimited to the old age who were suffering with joint pain.
2. The study was limited to small sample size.
3. The samples taken were only 30 for the experimental group and 30 for the control group.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for research study presents the measurement on which the purposes of the proposed study are based. The framework provides the perspective from which the investigator views the problem. The study was designed to assess the effectiveness of hot water compress with Epsom salt on old age people with joint pain.

A conceptual framework selected for the study is based on Imogene King's model. Health is viewed as both a state and process of being and becoming integrated and whole reflects the mutuality of people and environment. According to this model the goal is to facilitate adoption of individual for various stimuli from environment. The study is designed to evaluate the effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom salt among old age with joint pain

The study was based on the concept of assessing the pain perception before and after hot water compress with Epsom salt. The investigator adopted the Modified Imogene King's goal attainment theory. The theory assumes that humans are open systems and are having constant interaction with their environment. The major concepts in this theory of goal attainment are interacting, perception, communication, transaction, role, stress, growth and development, time, and space.

The definitions of these concepts are as follows:

Interaction

King proposed an open system model as a basis for her goal attainment theory. According to King all systems are open in that there is a continual exchange of matter energy and information. Open system has verified degree of interaction with the input and gives feed backs. In this study the nurse explains the hot water compress with Epsom salt procedure and gets their consent for research.

Perception

According to Imogene M. King, it is the primary features of the personal system because it influence all the other behaviors, refers to a person's representation of reality. In this study, the old age persons consistent with different demographic variables (age, gender, education, occupation, monthly income, religion, type of diet, joint pain duration, treatment, exercise, and type of exercise) which influence their behaviors related to hot water application with Epsom salt.

Environment

Environment is an open system that allows the exchange of matter, energy, and information. In this study the environment was the Male and Female selected areas at Kondapur, Sangareddy dist.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Review of literature is key step in research process. Review of literature refers to an extensive, exhaustive, and systemic examination of publications relevant to the research project. Review of literature is defined as a broad,

comprehensive in-depth, systematic, and critical review of scholarly publications, unpublished scholarly print materials, audiovisual materials, and personal communications.

According to Polit and Hunglar, the literature review is defined as "a critical summary of research on a topic of interest often prepared to put a research problem in context". Literature review helps to lay the foundations for the study. It provides the background for understanding the current knowledge on Illustration the significance of the new study. The investigator assembles knowledge by reviewing the literature of a selected problem and is presented under the following headings.

Section A: Review of literature related to joint pain in old age.

Section B: Review of literature related to the effectiveness of hot water application with joint pain.

Section C: Review of literature related to the effectiveness of Epsom salt, hot application.

Section D: Review of literature Studies related to joint pain joint pain in old age.

Pytel A, Wrzosek Zetal (2012) conducted a preliminary study to estimate patient knowledge on joint pain in the range of their own disease in South Hill. A self-made questionnaire was used for studies, aimed at obtaining basic information about clients with diagnosed joint pain. The sample included 270 people with joint pain. The examined clients were divided into 2 groups according to gender. The condition of knowledge of old age on their disease is higher and higher. It was revealed that the interest in obtaining information on the disease is higher in people with higher education both in women and men. Independent of age, the main source of knowledge on the disease is a doctor, physiotherapist, or a nurse. Educational deficiency in therapeutic teams was revealed, which indicates the

METHODOLOGY

This chapter includes the research approach, research design, variables the setting of the study, sampling technique, development, and description of tool intervention, valid of tool, reliability, pilot study. It further deals with the procedure for data collection and planning for data analysis.

Research Approach

The research approach tells the researcher from where the data is to be collected, what is to be collected, how to collect and how to analyze them. It also suggests a conclusion and helps the researcher in answering specific research questions in an accurate and efficient way.

The research approach adopted for this study is an evaluative research approach. This study aims at assessing the effectiveness of hot water compress with Epsom salt in reliving joint pain.

Research Design

The research design is an overall plan for obtaining answers to the research questions or for assessing the research hypothesis.

The research design adapted for the present study was the pre-test, post-test only design. In this study the subjects were randomly assigned to either the experimental or the control group. Effect of the dependent variable on both

the groups is seen before the treatment (pretest). Later, the treatment is conducted on experimental group only, and after treatment observation of dependent variable is made on both the groups to examine the effect of the manipulation of independent variable on the dependent variable.

2

Settings Of the Study:

The study is the location in which the study is conducted.

The study will be conducted in Kondapur. The sample of 60 old age clients was selected for the main study at Kondapur, sangareddy dist. Pilot study was conducted at sadashivpet, sangareddy dist., Ts.

Population

Polit and beck specifies the population is the entire asset of individual or objects having some characteristics. The target population for the present study was old ages with joint pain both male and female age group between 60 to 79 years. Accessible population for the present study was old age with joint who were available during the study at kondapur and sadashivpet,.

Sample And Sample Size

Sample refers to subjects of a population selected to participate in a research study. Sample consist of a total number of 60 subjects with joint pain among old age between the age group 60 to 79 at kondapur, sangareddy dist.

Sampling Technique

Sampling technique used for the present study was simple random sampling technique. The required number of joint pain subjects was selected as the sample.

Criteria For Sample Selection

The sample was selected based on the following inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

1. The study participants who were able to understand Telugu, English and Hindi.
2. The study participants were willing to give consent.
3. The study participants were available at the time of data collection.
4. The study participants who have joint pain.

Exclusion Criteria

5. Old age clients with severe neuropathies, burns, skin lesion on the joints.
6. Old age clients with complicated like neuropathies, vascular compromise, and systemic lupus erythematosus.

Description Of Variables

1. Independent variables — The variable that is believed to cause or influence the dependent variable. The independent variable in the present study is Hot water application with Epsom salt.
2. Dependent variables — The variable that is believed to hypothesis to depend on or to be caused by the independent variable is dependent variable. The dependent variable in the present study is Joint pain among old age.
3. Extraneous variables - which could influence the effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom salt among old age with joint pain are; Age, gender, education, occupation, monthly income, religion, type of diet, joint pain duration, treatment, type of exercise and exercise pattern.

Development And Description of Tool

The tools for the study had two sections.

Section - A

Had question about the collection of demographic data. The researcher developed it. It had 11 questions with multiple options. The study participants had to tick the appropriate boxes. It had questions related to age, gender, education, occupation, monthly income, religion, type of diet, joint pain duration a, treatment, type of exercise and exercise pattern.

Section – B

Pain Numerical Rating Scale. It is a standardized tool. The scoring key is given below.

Min=0 Max=10 Scoring key

Description	Rater	score
No pain	0	
Mild pain	1-3	
Moderate pain	4-6	
Severe	7-9	
Worst pain	10	

Figure 1: Pain Intensity Scale(0-10)

Intervention On Hot Water Application with Epsom Salt

Old aged will be given hot water application with Epsom salt for the affected joint which has pain. This should be done for 20 minutes daily for ten days with hot water compress with Epsom salt. The questions were asked to assess the subjective effect of hot water compress with Epsom salt like relaxation, smoothening, pain relief etc. among the old age .

Reliability

After pilot study reliability of the tool was assessed by using interpreter method and its correlation coefficient r ±value was 0.9. This correlation coefficient was extremely high, and it was a good tool for evaluating the effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom salt in reducing joint pain among old age with joint pains in selected areas at Kondapur, sangareddy dist.

Pilot Study

The pilot study was conducted in kondapur, sangareddy dist. during the week to test the feasibility of the study, a pilot study was conducted among 10 clients in the same manner as final study. Old age people with non-specific joint pain were selected using a simple random sampling technique for the purpose of the pilot study. They were assessed for pain perception on the first day using the research tools. After the pre assessment, hot water application with Epsom salt was given twice a day for ten consecutive days. At the end of the hot water compresses with Epsom salt therapy, after a week, the subjects were assessed again for pain using the research tool. The tool was found to be satisfactory in terms of simplicity and clarity. Based on the findings of the pilot study it was concluded that it was feasible and practicable to conduct the main study and criterion measures were found to be effective.

Data Collection Procedure

During the 1st visit, the researcher introduced herself, explained the purpose of the study, and confirmed the willingness of the old age clients to participate in the study as per the inclusion criteria. The objective of the study was explained. Based on the criteria experimental groups were selected and the intervention was given for 3weeks. Epsom salt compress was prepared by adding 30 grams of Epsom salts to one liter of boiling water (The temperature of the boiling water was as tolerated by the client) creating a hot compress by dipping a clean washcloth in the boiling water, wringing it out, and applying over the joint in which pain was present, twice a day, relieves the joint pain.

Plan for Data Analysis

After the data collection, the collected data were organized, tabulated, summarized, and analyzed. The data were analyzed according to the objectives of the study using descriptive and inferential statistics.

1. Analysis of the frequency and percentage distribution of the demographic data.
2. Hypothesis related to the effectiveness of Hot water compress with Epsom salt therapy, reducing the pain perception was evaluated using student paired "t" test, mean and standard deviation and Mc Nemar Chi- square test, test of significance.
3. Student independent "t" tests were used to find out association between the level of pain and selected demographic variables.

Figure 2: Schamatic Prepresentaion of Research Methodology.

DATA ANALYSIS

Analysis is the appraisal of the data and interpretation of the data consisting of a relation between the findings of the study of the research problem and theoretical framework of the study. An important function of the process of interpretation is to link the findings of the study to the mainstream of scientific knowledge in the field.

The data collected from 60 samples (30 in experimental group and 30 in control group) of clients with joint pain were analyzed, classified, and tabulated based on the objectives of the study.

The analysis and interpretation of data was based on data collection and the results were computed by using descriptive and inferential statistics. The study findings of the samples were presented in the following sections.

Organization of Data

The findings of the study were grouped and analyzed under the following section.

1. **Section A:** Assessment of demographic variables in effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom salt among old age with joint pain in Experimental and Control group.
2. **Section B:** Assessment of pre-test and post intervention of effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom salt among old age with joint pain in Experimental and control group.
3. **Section C:** Comparison of Pretest and post-test of effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom salt among old age with joint pain in experimental group.
4. **Section D:** Comparison of Pre-test and post-test of effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom salt among old age with joint pain in control group.
5. **Section E:** Association with post-test pain level with effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom salt among old age with joint pain in Experimental group, with their selected demographic variables.

Section-A

Assessment of demographic variables in effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom salt among old age with joint pain in Experimental and Control group.

Table 1: Frequency and percentage distribution of joint pain among old age according to their AGE N=60

AGE	Experimental Group n ₁ = 30		Control Group n ₂ = 30	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
60-64 years	15	50.0	13	43.3
65-69 years	8	26.7	13	43.3
70-74 years	3	10.0	4	13.3
75-79 years	4	13.3		0.0

TOTAL	30	100	30	100
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The above table shows that out of 30 joint pain clients in experimental group 15 (50.0%) were in the age group of 60-64 years, 8(26.7%) were in the age group of 65-69 years, 3 (10.0%) were in 70-74 years, 4(13.3%) were in 75-79 years . Out of 30 in the control group 13(43.3%) were in the age group of 60-64 years,13(43.3%) were in 65-69 years,4(13.3%) were in 70-74 years, were in 75-79 years. This concludes that out of 60 joint pain clients in experimental group and control group majority of them 15 & 13 (50.0% & 43.3%) were in the age group of 60-64 & 60-64 years, minority of them 3&0 (10.0% & 0.0%) were in the age group of 70-74 & 75-79 years.

Table 2: Frequency and percentage distribution of joint pain among old age according to their Gender N=60

Gender	Experimental Group n ₁ = 30		Control Group n ₂ = 30	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Male	11	36.7	5	16.7
Female	19	63.3	25	83.3

TOTAL	30	100	30	100
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The above table shows that out of 30 joint pains among old age in experimental group 11(36.7%) were males and 19(63.3%) were females. Out of 30 in control group 5(16.7%) were males and only 25(83.3%) were females. This concludes that out of 60 joint pains among old age in experimental group and control group majority of them 11&5(36.7% & 16.7%) were males, few of them 19&25 (63.3% & 83.3%) were females.

Table 3: Frequency and percentage distribution of joint pain among old age according to their Education N=60

Education	Experimental Group n ₁ = 30		Control Group n ₂ = 30	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Illiterate	7	23.3	8	26.7
Primary Education	6	20.0	7	23.3
Secondary Education	7	23.3	7	23.3

degree	7	23.3	5	16.7
Non formal education	2	6.7	2	6.7
PG and above	1	3.3	1	3.3
TOTAL	30	100	30	100

The above table shows that out of 30 joint pains among old age experimental group 7(23.3%)were in illiterate , 6(20.0%)were having primary education, 7(23.3%)were having secondary education, were in Degree , 2(6.7%) were having non formal education, 1(3.3%) were having PG and above. Out of 30 in control group, 8(26.7%)were in illiterate, 7(23.3%)were having primary education, 7(23.3%) were having secondary education, 5(16.7%) were in Degree, 2(6.7%) were having non formal education, 1 (3.3%) were having PG and above. This concludes that out of 30 joint pains among old age in experimental group majority of them 7(23.3%) were illiterates, secondary education and Degree, minority of them 1(3.3%) were PG and above. Out of 30 in the Control group most of them 8(26.7%) were Illiterate, were PG and above.

Table 4: Frequency and percentage distribution of joint pain among old age according to their Occupation
 N=60

Occupation	Experimental Group n ₁ = 30		Control Group n ₂ = 30	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Home Maker	9	30	10	33.3
Daily Wages	6	20.0	7	23.3
Self-employee	6	20.0	5	16.7
Government Employee	7	23.3	6	20.0
Private Employee	2	6.7	2	6.7
TOTAL	30	100	30	100

The above table shows that out of 30 joint pains among old age experimental group 9(30%)were homemakers, 6(20.0%) were having daily wages, 6(20.0%) were self-employee, 7(23.3%) were Government Employee, 2(6.7%) were Private Employee. Out of 30 in control group, 10(33.3%)were homemakers, 7(23.3%) were having Daily wages, 5(16.7%) were self-employees, 6(20.0%) were Government employees, 2(6.7%) were private employees. This concludes that out of

30 joint pains among old age in experimental group majority of them 9(30.0%) were home makers, and minority of them 2(6.7%)were private employees. out of 30 in the control group most of them IO(33.3%)were homemakers, 2(6.7%)were private employees.

Table 5: Frequency and percentage distribution of joint pain among old age according to their Income
 N=60

Income	Experimental Group n ₁ = 30		Control Group n ₂ = 30	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 5000	16	53.3	11	36.7
Rs 5001- 10000	4	13.3	8	26.7
Rs 10001-15000	7	23.3	9	30.0
More than 15001	3	10.0	2	6.7
TOTAL	30	100	30	100

The above table shows that out of 30 joint pains among old age experimental group 16(53.3%)were getting less than Rs 5000, 4(13.3%)were getting Rs 5001-10000, 7(23.3%)were getting 10001-15000 ,3(10.0%) were getting more than Rs 15001. Out of 30 in control group,11 (36.7%) were getting less than Rs 5000, were getting Rs 5001-10000,9 (30.0%) were

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getting 10001-15000, were getting more than Rs 15001. This concludes that out of 30 joint pains among old age in experimental group majority of them 16(53.3%) were getting less than Rs 5000, and minority of them were more than Rs 15001. out of 30 in the control group most of them 11(36.7%)were getting less than Rs 5000, and minority of them 2(6.7%)were getting more than Rs 15001.

Table 6: Frequency and percentage distribution of joint pain among old age according to their Religion

N=60

Religion	Experimental Group n ₁ = 30		Control Group n ₂ = 30	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Hindu	14	46.7	15	15.0
Muslim	6	20.0	5	6.7
Christian	7	23.3	9	30.0
Others	3	10.0	1	3.3
TOTAL	30	100	30	100

The above table shows that out of 30 joint pains among old age in experimental group 14(46.7%) are Hindus, 6(20.0%) are Muslims, 7(23.3%) are Christians, 3(10.0%) are from other religion. Out of 30 in control group, 15(50.0%) are Hindus, 5(16.7%) are Muslims, 9(30.0%) are Christians, 1(3.3%) are from others. This concludes that out of 30 joint pains among old age in experimental group and control groups majority of them 14 & 15 (46.7% & 50.0%) were from Hindu religion, only 3 & 1 (10.0% & 3.3%) were from other religion.

Table 7: Frequency and percentage distribution of joint pain among old age according to their type of Diet

N=60

Type of Diet	Experimental Group n ₁ = 30		Control Group n ₂ = 30	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Vegetarian	13	43.4	10	33.3
Non vegetarian	17	56.7	20	66.7
TOTAL	30	100	30	100

The above table shows that out of 30 joint pains among old age in experimental group 13 (43.3%) were vegetarian, 17(56.7%) were non vegetarians. Out of 30 in control group 10(33.3%) were vegetarian, 20(66.7%) were non vegetarians. This concludes that out of 30 joint pains among old age in experimental group most of them were 17(56.7%) Non vegetarian & minority of them 13(43.3%) were vegetarian ,out of 30 in the control group most of them 20 (66.7%) were non vegetarians. And minority of them 10(33 were vegetarian.

Table 8 : Frequency and percentage distribution of Joint pain among old age according to their duration of illness
 N = 60

Duration Of Illness	Experimental Group n1= 30		Control Group n2= 30	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 6 months	9	30.0	13	43.3

6 month- 1 years	9	30.0	5	6.7
1 year - 2 years	10	33.3	8	26.7
More than 2 years	2	6.7	4	13.3
TOTAL	30	100	30	100

The above table shows that out of 30 old aged with joint pain, experimental group 9 (30.0%) were suffering with joint pain less than 6 months, 9(30.0%) were suffering with joint pain since 6 months to I year, 10(33.3%) were suffering with joint pain since 1 year to 2 years, 2(6.7%) were suffering with joint pain more than 2 year.

Out of 30 in control group, 13(43.3%)were suffering with joint pain less than 6 months, 5(6.7%) were suffering with joint pain since 6 months to 1 year, 8(26.7%) were suffering with joint pain since 1 year to 2 year, 4(13.3%) were suffering with join pain more than 2 years.

This concludes that out of 30 joint pains among old age in experimental group majority of them 10(33.3%) were suffering with joint pain since I year to 2 years, and minority of them 2(6.7%)were suffering with joint pain more than 2 years,. out of 30 in the control group most of them 13 (43.3%) suffering with joint pain less than 6 months, and minority of them 4(13.3%)were suffering with joint pain more than 2 years.

Table 9: Frequency and percentage distribution of joint pain among old age according to their duration of treatment N=60

Duration Of Treatment	Experimental Group n ₂ = 30		Control Group n ₂ = 30	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 6 months	11	36.7	16	53.3
6 months- 1 years	11	36.7	4	13.3
1 year - 2 years	7	23.3	5	16.7
More than 2 years	1	3.3	5	16.7
TOTAL	30	100	30	100

The above table shows that out of 30 joint pains among old age experimental group 11 (36.7%) were taking medication for joint pain less than 6 months, 11(36.7%)were taking medication for joint pain since 6 months to 1 year, 7(23.3%)were taking medication for joint pain since I year to 2 years, 1 (3.3%) were taking medication for joint pain more than 2 year.

Out of 30 in control group, 16(53.3%)were taking medication for joint pain less than 6 months, 4(13.3%) were taking medication for joint pain since 6 months to 1 year, 5(16.7%) were taking medication for joint pain since I year to 2 year, 5(16.7%) were taking medication for join pain more than 2 years.

This concludes that out of 30 joint pains among old age in experimental group most of them 11 & 11 (36.7 & 36.7%) were taking medication for joint pain less than 6 months & 6 months to since 1 year , and minority of them 1(3.3%)were taking medication for joint pain more than 2 years,. out of 30 in the control group most of them 16(53.3%)were taking medication for joint pain less than 6 months, and minority of them 5&5(16.7& 16.7%)were taking medication for joint pain 1 year to 2 year and more than 2 years.

Table 10: Frequency and percentage distribution of joint pain among old age according to their types of Excises
 N=60

Excises	Experimental Group n ₂ = 30	Control Group n ₂ = 30

	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Walking	16	53.3	18	60.0
Breathing Exercise	8	26.7	4	13.3
Yoga	5	16.7	7	23.3
Jogging	1	3.3	1	3.3
TOTAL	30	100	30	100

The above table shows that out of 30 joint pains among old age in experimental group 16(53.3) were doing Walking, 8 (26.7%) were doing Breathing Exercises,5(16.7%) were doing yoga, I (3.3%) were doing jogging, out of 30 in control group 18 (60.0%) were doing walking, 4(13.3%) were doing Breathing exercises,7(23.3%) were doing Yoga I (3.3%) were doing Jogging. This concludes that out of 30 joint pains among old age in experimental group majority of them 16(53.3%) were doing Walking and minority of them 1 (3.3%) were doing jogging and out 30 in control group majority of them 18(60.0%) were doing Walking and minority of them I (3.3%) were doing Jogging.

Table 11: Frequency and percentage distribution of joint pain among old age according to their Excise Patterns N=60

Excise Patterns	Experimental Group n ₂ = 30	Control Group n ₂ = 30

	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Regular	15	50.0	16	53.3
Irregular	13	43.3	14	46.7
Never	2	6.7	-	0.0
TOTAL	30	100	30	100

The above table shows that out of 30 joint pains among old age in experimental group 15 (50.0%) were doing exercises Regularly, 13(43.3%) were doing exercise irregularly 2(6.7%) were not doing any exercise. Out of 30 in control group 16(53.3%) were doing exercise Regularly, 14(46.7%) were doing exercises Irregularly. This concludes that out of 30 joint pain among old age in experimental group majority of them 15(50.0%) were doing exercises regularly and minority of them 2(6.7%) were not doing any exercise . Out of 30 in control group majority of them 16 (53.3%) were doing exercises Regularly, 0(0.0%) were never doing any exercises.

Section-B:

Assessment of pre-test and post intervention of effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom salt among old age with joint pain in Experimental and control group.

Table 12: Frequency and percentage distribution of pre-intervention of effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom salt among old age with joint pain in experimental group. N = 60

Pain level	Experimental Group n ₂ = 30		Control Group n ₂ = 30	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
No Pain	0	0	0	0
Mild Pain	0	0	0	0
Moderate Pain	0	0	0	0
Severe Pain	15	50.0	14	46.7
Worst	15	50.0	16	53.3
TOTAL	30	100	30	100

The above table shows that of 60 joint pains among old age in experimental group and control group all of them 30 where in experimental group and 30 where in control group.

Table 13: Frequency and percentage distribution of post-intervention of effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom salt among old age with joint pain in experimental group. N = 60

Pain level	Experimental Group n ₂ = 30		Control Group n ₂ = 30	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
No Pain	0	0	0	0
Mild Pain	19	63.3	0	0.0
Moderate Pain	11	36.7	0	0.0
Serve Pain	0	0.0	17	56.7

Worst	0	0.0	13	43.3
TOTAL	30	100	30	100

The above table shows that of 30 joint pains among old age in experimental group majority of them 19(63.3%) were suffering with mild joint pain, minority of them 0(0.0%) were reduce pain level compare with pretest joint pain level,. Out of 30 control groups most of them 17(56.7%) were suffering with severe joint pain.

SECTION - C

Comparison of Pretest and post-test of effectiveness of hot water Epsom salt among old age with joint pain in experimental group.

Table 14: Mean, standard deviation and paired 't' test values of pre and Post-test of effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom salt among old age with joint pain in experimental group.

S. NO	Joint Pain level	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Old age Paired t- test
1.	Pretest	30	9.30	0.702	t=19.191 df=29

2.	Post test	30	3.10	1.539	p=0.000 ***
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* Significant- $p < 0.05$ ** Highly Significant- $p < 0.001$ *** Very Highly Significant- $p < 0.0001$

The above table reveals that the joint pain level in post assessment is reduced when comparing with the pre assessment of joint pain level among old age in experimental group . The mean score of pre assessment is 9.30 and post assessment is 3.10. This shows the hypothesis of the study was proved . the t- value is 19.191 with $df=29$ and $p=0.000$. is statistically significant.

Section D

Comparison of Pre-test and post-test of effectiveness of hot water Epsom salt among old age with joint pain control group.

Table 15: Mean, standard deviation and paired 't' test values of pre and Post of effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom salt among old age with joint pain control group.

S. NO	Joint pain level	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Old age Paired t-test
1.	Pretest	30	9.47	0.629	t=1.439 df=29 p=0.161
2.	Post test	30	9.33	0.606	

The above table shows the joint pain level in post assessment is not reduced when compared with the pre assessment of joint pain among old age in control group. The mean score of pre assessment is 9.47 and post assessment is 9.33 the $p=0.161$ and it is statistically not significant.

Section — E

Association with post-test pain level with effectiveness of hot water Epsom salt among old age with joint pain in Experimental group, with their selected demographic variables.

Table 16:

S.NO	Demographic variables	value	Table value	Degree of freedom	LOS
1	Age	0.664	1.579	3	NS
2	Gender	0.447	0.578	1	NS
3	Education	0.570	3.855	5	NS
4	Occupation	0.041	9.973	4	NS
5	Monthly income	0.215	4.470	3	NS
6	Religion	0.065	7.239	3	NS
7	Dietary pattern	0.346	0.889	1	NS
8	Duration of illness	0.742		3	NS
9	Duration of treatment	0.439	2.709	3	NS
10	Type of exercise	0.26	9.222	3	NS
11	Exercise pattern	0.400	1.833	2	NS

L O S = Level of significant S = Significant N S = non-significant

SUMMARY, FINDINGS, LIMITATIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary: The present study was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom Salt among old age with joint pain at selected areas at Kondapur, Sangareddy dist., Ts. Evaluative research approach was used for this study. The conceptual framework used for this study was Imogene King's Goal Attainment Theory Model. Hot water

application with Epsom Salt among old age with joint pain to evaluate knowledge on joint pain management of selected areas. The collected data were analyzed with the help of descriptive and inferential statistical analysis of collected data."

Major Findings of The Study:

The findings are discussed under the following objectives:

Findings Related to Demographic Variables:

1. majority of them 15 (50.0%) were in the age group of 60-64 years in experimental and 13&13(43.3%&43.3%)were in the age group of 60-64&6569 years in control group.
2. Majority of them 19(63.3%) were females in experimental group and 25(83.3%) were females in Control group.
3. Majority of them 7&7&7(23.3%&23.3%&23.3%) were Illiterate, Secondary Education and Degree were in Experimental group and 8(26.7%) were Illiterate in control group.
4. Majority of them 9(30.0%) were home maker in Experimental group and 10(33.3%) were Home Maker in Control group.
5. Majority of them 16(53.3%) were getting less than 5000/- in Experimental group and 11(36.7%) were getting less than 5000/- in Control group.
6. Majority of them 14(46.7%) were Hindu in Experimental group and 15(50.0%) were Hindu in Control group.
7. Majority of them 17(56.7%) were non vegetarian in Experimental group and 20(66.7%) were non vegetarian in Control group.
8. Majority of them 10(33.3%) were suffering with joint pain since1-2 year in experimental group and 13(43.3%) were suffering with joint pain less than 6 months in Control group.
9. Majority of them 11 & 11(36.7 & 36.7%) were taking medication less than6. months and 6 months to 1 year in Experimental group and 16(53.3 %) were taking medication less than 6 month in Control group.
10. Majority of them 16(53.3%) were doing walking in Experimental group and 18(60.0%) were walking in control group.
11. Majority of them 15(50.0%) were doing exercises regularly in Experimental group and were doing exercises regularly in Control group.

Finding Based on The Objectives

To assess the level of pain in both experimental and control group by pretest .

Data analysis shows that 15&15 (50.0%&50.0%) had severe and worst pain level in Experimental group by pre-test and whereas in post-test 0(0.0%) were decreased pain level in severe and worst pain level in experimental group. In control group 16(53.3%) were having worst pain in pre-test, whereas in post-test pain level decreased up to 0(0.0%).

To compare the pre and post-test level of hot water application with Epsom Salt among old age with joint pain.

Data analysis shows that mean post test score of joint pain of 3.10 with standard deviation of I .539 was significantly higher than the mean pre-test score of joint pain 9.30 with standard deviation of 0.702. The paired 't' value was 19.191 which was significant at level.0.000

Therefore **H1**: There is significantly increase in post-test level of hot water application with Epsom Salt among old age.

To determine the association between post-test level of pain among old age in their selected demographic variables.

Chi-square value showed that, demographic variable such as Age, gender, education, occupation, monthly income, religion, type of diet, duration of illness, duration of taking medication, exercise and exercise pattern had no association with hot water application with Epsom salt among old age with joint pain.

Therefore **H2** : There is a significant association between posttest of hot water application with Epsom salt among old age with joint pain with socio demographic variables such as occupation ,and exercise had an association with hot water application with Epsom Salt among old age with joint pain.

CONCLUSION

The study was conducted to assess the effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom Salt among old age with joint pain the mean score was 3.10 with standard deviation 1.539. So, the hot water application with Epsom Salt was effective method to relieve joint pain among old age.

Implications In Nursing

The findings of the study were implemented in four areas such as nursing practice, nursing education, nursing administration and nursing research.

Nursing Practice

The old age need to be in a safe and supportive environment and an active participant in the health care.

Nursing Education

The nurse educators would be needed to provide adequate knowledge towards hot water application with Epsom Salt by providing information. Every phase of nursing educator will be influenced by the philosophy upon which it is based philosophy take in all aspects of human life with the view in regulating and protecting life therefore, it is the primary concept of the nurse. From the finding of the study, it is evident that there is improvement of effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom Salt among old age with joint pain.

Nursing Administration

Nursing administration need to organize in service and continuing education programs, workshops, conferences to enhance their knowledge regarding effectiveness of hot water application with Epsom Salt among old age with joint pain.

Nursing Research

It help to make evidence-based nursing practice in various areas. A profession seeking to improve the practice of its member and to enhance its professional strive for the continual development of the relevant body knowledge nursing research represent a critically important tool for the nursing profession to acquire such knowledge.

Nursing Service

Nurses should maintain standards in providing nursing care to joint pain among old age. She should improve standard of care by updating her knowledge and skills.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of the study following recommendations were made

1. A similar study can be conducted in large sample size to generalize the study findings.
2. A comparative study can be conducted on effectiveness hot water application with Epsom Salt among old age with joint pain at selected areas.
3. A similar study can be conducted in different settings and in different socio-economic strata.

LIMITATIONS

1. The research of file difficulty in getting cooperation from few illiterate people in community area due to lack of interest.
1. Findings are limited setting only.

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